

Student alienation and perceived organizational culture: A correlational study

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ABSTRACT

It is generally expected that the students are supposed to gain an engaging and enriching experience throughout their journey of higher education. The educational institutions have to take up the responsibility to ensure that students are engaged meaningfully and are in a state of well-being. However, in the present scenario, students at colleges and universities have started to feel alienated from the campus life. Research shows that alienation levels are rising among the youth. Factors like stress, coping mechanism, restrictive parental behavior, peer pressure, academic performance, and organizational culture have an impact on alienation among the students. This study attempts to understand the relationship between student alienation and organizational culture in an educational institution. The study employed a descriptive correlational design and collected data from 600 under graduate students studying in a university. The study used student alienation scale and organizational culture assessment instrument to collect the survey data. Study revealed that there is a negative correlation between student alienation and organizational culture. There were 30% variation in student alienation is explained by different types of organizational culture. Clan culture reduces student alienation compared to hierarchy culture. The researchers urge for further research to identify ideal organizational cultures that can promote student engagement and student well-being.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Higher education is a vital stage in the entire educational process. It plays a crucial role in producing responsible and productive citizens. An effective higher education system is a must for a nation aiming at growth and development. It should offer students all those learning experiences that would contribute to their personal growth and realization of their potentials. The higher education institutions in any country should involve opportunities for learning, adopt student-centered approaches to their decision-making, provide real-life experiences, and develop research skills. Higher education institutions must provide experiences that shape the life of each student on the campus.

All higher educational institutions follow a particular culture. This culture refers to the assignment of roles and duties, decision-making processes, reward systems, communication flow, and other administrative aspects. Institutional culture shapes the university atmosphere and determines the overall impression institutions will have on students. The study of organizational culture has gained relevance and significance in the 21st century. Staff members of an institution attempt to attach meaning to their workplace

and students put efforts in choosing the best institutions that suits their needs and future goals. Thus, organizational culture plays a vital role in higher education. Organizational culture has a positive impact on students and communities. Therefore a deeper understanding of organizational culture is necessary in establishing an innovative climate that helps the higher education institutions to impact students, societies, and countries positively [1].

In the context of a university, culture can be defined as the values and beliefs of all associated members such as administrators, professors, students, people on board of studies, and support staff. Culture is established based on the traditions and practices that are communicated through various mediums [2]. University culture might also be viewed as the personality of an organization. By looking at the campus facility maintenance, architectural styles, construction of buildings, and student interactions and attire, one can understand institution's culture. The institutional leaders and administrators are increasingly becoming aware of this idea of culture and its crucial role in growth and development of the university [2].

The primary focus, in this study, is to view organizational culture through the lens of a student. This study stresses the student's perspective of the university's organizational culture so that relationships can be drawn between the perceived organizational culture and experience and engagement that the student gains in the Institution. Kahu and Nelson points out that student's self-efficacy, emotions, belonging, and well-being plays a significant role with institutional characteristics and leads to student engagement and success [3].

Students' learning experiences in higher education are becoming increasingly important today. In order to gain a profound understanding of the learning experience of students, there is a need to delve deeper into the social and psychological aspects of student engagement. We need to understand: i) What motivates the students?; ii) What engages them?; iii) What enables their growth?; and iv) What are their expectations in terms of having a good experience in an institution? The concepts of engagement and alienation can give a broader understanding of the learning experiences that a student gets in a higher education institution. Student alienation is an issue that is visible worldwide, including developed and under-developing countries. To deal with the problem of alienation, we need to look at the engagement of students in the educational process. The environment in which the students are placed is paramount in determining the engagement and disengagement of students. Almrott, *et al.* found that difference in educational culture affect the process and outcome of undergraduate students [4].

Understanding the concept of student-alienation becomes critical today since their life-style is rapidly undergoing changes. It is taking them away from their own psychosocial needs, emotional needs, value system, and family. Students these days even started staying away from the community. Boredom, isolation, and meaninglessness are the emerging concerns. Alienation can even turn to violence. Altay and Ceyhan found a positive relationship between student alienation and attitude towards violence [5]. Alienation is a condition wherein one is detached from one's own self, other people, and the society as a whole. It must be noted that alienation as a term has adopted various meanings, including loneliness, isolation, and a sense of aimlessness, anomie, and various others. The definition in Oxford English Dictionary suggests that alienation is feeling of being isolated or unengaged from an activity or group of people [6].

In any educational institution, students not just learn the content given in the syllabi, but from everything they see around themselves. The entire culture and functioning of the university would have an impact on the students, their learning experience, their participation and engagement, their academic performance, and their personality as a whole. In the present day scenario, wherein educational institutions are initiating efforts to offer the best possible learning experiences to the students and emphasize wellbeing and happiness among people, the study of practices and organizational culture of institutions becomes even more imperative [7].

The significance of promoting students' engagement at the university, the growing alienation among students, and the idea that perceived institutional culture can affect students' experiences and is the driving force for researchers to understand the relationship between student alienation and organizational culture. The study attempts to find the relationship between student alienation and organizational culture. The extent to which perceived organizational culture predicts student alienation. The study draws its sample from an Indian University, as this university is a growing institution housing around 20,000 students. It would be significant to study a university imparting education to a huge number of students as well as the one being in the list of leading educational institutions. Growing universities are compelled to work on various practices and improve, and hence such studies would help the university to enhance the culture and make it ideal for the students. The findings of the study will help the stakeholders to reduce student alienation and sow positive organizational culture to reap the optimum output from the students.

The introduction section mentions the context of the research, problem statement, and proposed solution. Literature review section has synthesized the existing studies and identified the research gap. After review, the article includes a methodology section that explains the methods adopted, sample selected, procedure of data collection, and statistical analysis employed. Post the methodology, researchers put forth

the results and discussions, which highlights the new findings and compare it with the past studies. Finally, the paper ends with a conclusion section, which highlights the limitations of the study and provide suggestions for further research.

The review of related literature includes the mapping of research studies on student alienation and organizational culture from the year 1970 to 2020. It includes articles studied from Jstor, Proquest, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, handbook of sociology, and other online platforms such as Microsoft Academics, Base, and Core.

The term alienation is basically related with economic processes and has been propounded by Marx. Marx's work on alienation was published in 1844 and since then the concept has been debated and researched upon. Marx understood the term alienation in terms of the economic system and the experience of a laborer working for the owner. Marx describes alienation as a condition wherein the objects created by humanity appear as aliens to humans. People create their own society but will remain alienated until they recognize themselves in their own creation. Marx gives religion as an example wherein he stated, "Man makes religion, and religion does not make the man" [8]. People do not realize that they have created the religion, and they give powers to the god to control and direct their actions. People invest a lot in religion, and in this process, they lose themselves. What happens is that an external entity like religion has control over human destiny. According to Marx, alienation is at its peak in capitalistic societies wherein workers view their own selves as bounded by the market forces over which they have absolutely no control [8].

Apart from the Marxian theory of alienation, certain other perspectives to alienation have also been developed recently. Viewing from the postmodern perspective, says that alienation as a concept has much to contribute to the contemporary understanding of student learning, and suggests an array of theoretical perspectives that throw light on the possible genesis of the alienated student condition. Primarily, argues that alienation is an unavoidable consequence of the postmodern emphasis on utilitarianism, with functionality and competence being seen as the major aims of education. It also suggests how alienation can sprout from the difficulty faced by the student in entering the academic discourse, which tends to construct student identity in particular constraining ways [9].

Based on the review of related literature, it was in the time period 1960s-1970s that the idea of alienation was studied through an educational perspective and then student alienation as a variable emerged in the researches. In the beginning, it was studied with variables like academic performance, self-esteem, and other factors like social awareness and other family related variables. It was only after the year 2000 that Student alienation was studied with variables relating to the culture of the institution.

The concept of organizational culture has primarily stemmed from the disciplines of management. The term was first introduced by Jacques in his book 'The Changing Culture of A Factory' [10], [11]. Organizational culture has been widely researched upon in the field of management as well as in education. Organizational culture of higher education institutions can be explained with regard to following two aspects: the form and extent of control, and the emphasis on policy and strategy [12]. Types of organizational culture are highlighted as: i) Entrepreneurial, integrating strict policy and loose operational control, emphasizing on market, external opportunities, and relationships with stakeholders; ii) Corporate, having strict policy and operational control, hierarchy where the senior management has more power than executive authority; iii) Collegiate, having loose policy and liberal operational control, decentralization, stressing individual autonomy; iv) Bureaucratic, having a combination of loose policy and firm operational control, where the rules, regulations, and precedents are most important.

College culture is all about the underlying aspects like norms, values and beliefs, rituals and ceremonies, symbols, and stories that create the personality of the educational institution. These values and norms enable the molding of the way people think and work within the educational institutions. Institutional culture is about what is being done, what is heard, and how it is being directed [13].

Although there are studies that show the relationship of alienation to a few aspects of organizational culture like school bureaucratization, teacher control ideology, fairness of learning environment, it is only in the time period of 2000-2012 that studies on organizational culture and student engagement in higher education institutions are noticed.

A study conducted by Sookoo on perceptions of injustice and alienation dynamics within the work place found that procedural justice had direct effect on alienation of public sector employees [14]. Lower the level of organizational justice higher is the employee alienation. Fralinger and Olson found that the university had clan culture at that time and the students expected that clan culture must prevail in the future [2]. A study conducted by Velden [12] stated that the corporate and bureaucratic culture are not conducive for student engagement. Students voice out for clan culture in most of the studies reviewed in the present study. Latchigadu found that there is no relationship between organizational culture and organizational commitment [15]. According to Tomaszek, level of alienation is highest among gifted adolescents. There is no relationship between student alienation and creativity predisposition [16]. Yorulmaz, Altinkurt, and Yilmaz found that

teachers' organizational alienation differed among gender, school type, and experience. The study also finds a significant relationship between alienation and organizational professionalism [17]. Çağlar stated that the student had average alienation while having positive attitude towards teaching profession. There was a negative relationship between student alienation and attitude towards teaching profession [18]. According to Marcin, Morinaj, and Hascher, teacher injustice as an indicator for teacher-student relationship had significant association with alienation of learning [19]. Öksüz and Öztürk found that students' alienation is affected by class and parents' home city, gender, and number of siblings. However, there is no relationship between homesick attitude and alienation [20].

Majority of studies reviewed presented that student, particularly those belong to the age group of 18 to 22 years of age feel alienated due to various factors. Factors affecting alienation levels include demographic variables like class, gender, educational variables like achievement, motivation and other variables including parental pressure, school climate, teacher ideology, and fairness of learning environment. Thus, the issues of student alienation levels and factors affecting alienation become critical questions, which need addressing through research and practice.

The review puts forth many past studies which relate organizational culture with employees and their performance and motivation. In the educational context, many studies refer to culture in the educational institutions and its impact on teachers [21], [22]. However, few studies attempt to take organizational culture to the students. How students perceive the organizational culture and what is the kind of culture preferred by the students in higher educational institutions are some of the emerging questions and not many past studies have considered these questions. While the educational systems across the globe are aiming to incorporate student-centered approaches, it is crucial that students' perceptions play a role in determining the organizational culture of universities. Another noteworthy gap is the lack of similar studies conducted in the Indian context. Indian higher education system is growing and constitutes many reputed universities, which house students across the globe. Thus, it is of utmost importance that study of cultures at the Indian universities are undertaken.

The literature presented several tools that aim at the assessment of student alienation and organizational culture, which has enabled researchers to select the most relevant tools that fit the purpose of the present study. Past studies have shown that though assessment tools are not recently developed, they have been used repeatedly in the present context and hence these tools are valid. The assessment tools have provided a framework that can guide the entire study.

The purpose of this study are: i) To find out whether there is a relationship between student alienation and types of organizational culture; ii) To find out whether the student alienation is predicted by type of organizational culture; iii) To compare the percentage of the level of student-alienation across types of organizational culture.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The researcher attempts to understand the relationship between two variables: student alienation and organizational culture and hence a correlational research design has been selected. The correlation research design is generally used when the researcher wants to study if any one variable is related to the other variables and if the relationship exists, what is the extent and direction of the same. Under correlational research design, the approach selected by this study is quantitative research which focuses on numeric and objective data [23]. The requirement for this study was having a larger sample for better generalizations and in a quantitative approach, results are arrived based on larger representative sample.

The method selected for this study is descriptive survey research. Descriptive research involves studying and describing a particular area of interest as it is. Survey is a method that will allow the researcher to collect large amount of data. Survey not only allows for collecting data on one variable but also allows for establishing relationships between variables. Hence, descriptive survey research becomes the most relevant design for this study [24]. Earlier studies have only tried to understand the relationship between alienation and organizational professionalism but have not attempt understand the specific cause, hence in the present study an attempt made to understand whether specific type of organizational culture can predict the variation in student alienation by regression analysis.

2.1. Population and sample

Research has established that youth globally face a considerable level of alienation today due to various aspects like employment, academic pressures, family and peer pressures, stress, socio-political environment and others. Alienation among adolescents and youth is a major problem in India and across the globe. In the given context, it becomes important to study alienation among youth in India especially among students belonging to the age group of 18 to 22 years. There is no single agreed upon definition of youth.

United Nations defines youth as individuals belonging to the age group of 15 to 24 years [25]. For this study, the youth is defined as students belonging to the age group of 18 to 22 years.

Since this study is on student alienation in relation to organizational culture, the selection of an institution is also necessary. One of the top universities in India has been selected as it is a growing educational institute emphasizing the vision of excellence and service. Recently, Harvard has conducted a case study on how the institute has grown over time and how it has fostered a culture of learning, research, and growth among students and faculty [26]. Selected university also houses more than 18,000 students coming from across the country. Hence the University provides a large heterogeneous population for this study. Therefore, the population of the study involves all the second and third year undergraduate students in the university.

The sample selected for this study included 600 students from second and third year undergraduate courses in the university. First year students have not been involved in the study as there can be other factors responsible for alienation like adjustment to the new atmosphere, staying away from home or others. Simple random sampling was adopted and accordingly a sample of 600 students were selected.

2.2. Limitations of the study

The study has measured only the present organizational culture as perceived by students of the university and excluded the measurement of future organizational culture. The study did not analyze the dimensions of alienation scale but considered the overall score for each participant [27]. The study is also confined to one university which had a huge student strength of 18,000.

2.3. Measuring instruments

The present study used two instruments to collect the data. Study used the student alienation scale to measure the level of student alienation. Study used organizational culture assessment instrument [28] to measure the type of organizational culture as perceived by the students studying in the university. The researchers established the validity and reliability of both the instruments by conducting a pilot study.

2.4. Validity and reliability of the measuring instruments

Student alienation scale and organizational culture measuring instruments subjected to face validity and content validity by a panel of experts to verify the suitability of the content and construct to the present context of the study. A pilot study conducted to measure the reliability of the instruments. Instruments administered to a sample of 60 students. Cronbach's alpha internal consistency value of student alienation scale found to be 0.79 and for organizational culture instrument, Cronbach's alpha internal consistency value found to be 0.86. Instruments were found highly reliable [29].

2.5. Statistical analysis

A Pearson correlation test conducted to find out the relationship between student alienation and different types of organizational culture namely clan culture, adhocracy culture, market culture, and hierarchy culture. The test conducted on the software SPSS version 22; the output of the test presented in Table 1. Table 1 shows that exist negative correlation between the variables student alienation and organizational culture [30]. That means for a rise in particular type of organizational culture scores the student alienation score is decreasing. There is a moderate negative correlation between clan culture of the organization and student alienation ($r=-0.448$). There is a moderate negative correlation between adhocracy culture of the organization and student alienation ($r=-0.376$). There is a weak negative correlation between market culture of the organization and student alienation ($r=-0.273$). There is a weak negative correlation between hierarchy culture of the organization and student alienation ($r=-0.251$).

A regression statistical test conducted to understand the correlation between student alienation and organizational culture. Nevertheless, regression analysis explains the total variation in the student alienation (dependent variable) as explained by the organizational culture (independent variable) presented in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the correlation between student alienation and organizational culture is 0.539 indicating high degree of correlation. The 29.1% of the variation in student alienation is because of the organizational culture [31].

Table 1. Pearson correlation statistics

Variables	Organizational culture			
	Clan culture	Adhocracy	Market	Hierarchy
Student alienation	-0.448**	-0.376**	-0.273**	-0.251**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 2. Model summary statistics of regression

Model	R	R Square	Model summary ^a			
			Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	Change statistics	
					R Square change	F change
1	.539 ^a	.291	.286	10.331	.291	61.020

a. Predictors: (Constant), hierarchy culture, clan culture, market culture, adhocracy culture

Durbin-Watson statistical test conducted to find out the auto-correlation in the residuals from regression analysis. The result of the auto-correlation between student alienation and organizational culture presented in Table 3. From the Table 3 it is clear that, there is a slight positive autocorrelation among the variables organizational culture and student alienation as per Durbin-Watson statistics 1.276. It indicates that the positive correlation established between the variables will remain true in the future and thereby it establishes the consistency of the research output in the present study.

ANOVA output of the regression analysis presented in Table 4 explains how well the regression equation fits the data that means how well the organizational culture predicts student alienation. Table 4 shows that regression model significantly predicts the dependent variable ($p < 0.05$). It means organizational culture predicts student alienation and it is a good fit for the data.

Table 3. Durbin-Watson statistics

Model	Change Statistics			Durbin-Watson
	df1	df2	Sig. F change	
1	4 ^b	595	.000	1.276

b. Dependent variable: Alienation score

Table 4. ANOVA statistics

Model		ANOVA ^a				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26051.540	4	6512.885	61.020	.000 ^b
	Residual	63506.434	595	106.734		
	Total	89557.973	599			

a. Dependent variable: Alienation score

b. Predictors: (Constant), Hierarchy culture, clan culture, market culture, adhocracy culture

The regression model coefficients presented in Table 5 determine whether organizational culture statistically significantly contributes to the model. Table 5 shows that organizational culture contributes significantly to the model and be able to predict student alienation. Four regression equations are formed out of the unstandardized coefficients (B) values.

$$\text{Student alienation} = 65.710 + (-1.105) \times (\text{clan culture})$$

$$\text{Student alienation} = 65.710 + (-0.325) \times (\text{adhocracy culture})$$

$$\text{Student alienation} = 65.710 + (-0.513) \times (\text{market culture})$$

$$\text{Student alienation} = 65.710 + (-0.576) \times (\text{hierarchy culture})$$

The regression analysis histogram presented in Figure 1 represents the distribution of standardized residuals data and explains whether the data skewed and are there any outliers. It explains whether the assumptions under lying regression analysis met. Figure 1 shows that the residuals of the regression line are approximately normally distributed. Therefore, the data is suitable for regression analysis and statistical assumptions are met.

Table 5. Showing regression coefficients statistics

Model	Coefficients ^a					95.0% Confidence interval for B	
	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Lower bound	Upper bound
	B	Std. Error	Beta		Lower bound		
	(Constant)	65.710	2.909		59.998	59.998	71.423
	Clan culture	-1.105	.138	-.373	-1.376	-1.376	-.833
1	Adhocracy culture	-.325	.153	-.100	-.625	-.625	-.025
	Market culture	-.513	.129	-.159	-.766	-.766	-.260
	Hierarchy culture	-.576	.134	-.170	-.839	-.839	-.314

a. Dependent variable: Alienation score

Figure 1. Histogram of regression

The regression analysis normal probability plot presented in Figure 2 represents the residuals versus the expected values when the distribution is normal. From the Figure 2, it is clear that the data points are spread around the regression line and is approximately following a straight line. Therefore, the assumption residuals are normally distributed is met. Thus, regression analysis is possible.

The regression analysis scatter plot presented in Figure 3 represents the relationship between student alienation and organizational culture. It indicates whether the relationship is linear or non-linear. In other words, it indicates whether the variance of the residual in a regression model is constant. From the Figure 3, it is clear that the data is homoscedastic and thus indicates the linear relationship between the variables student alienation and organizational culture. It explains equal variances meaning, even if the data comes from different populations, the variance is equal.

Figure 2. P-P plot for regression

Figure 3. Scatterplot for regression

The cross tabulation statistical output presented in Table 6 is to understand the prevailing organizational culture versus level of student alienation in terms of percentage. From Table 6, it is clear that, if the organization culture is perceived as clan culture, then alienation level low (24.7%). If the organization culture is adhocracy, then alienation level is average (13.1%). If the organization culture is market, then alienation level is below average (38%). If the organization culture is hierarchy, then alienation level is high (80.6%). It is also evident as shown in Figure 4 [26].

Table 6. Showing the percentage of most prevailing culture in the organization versus level of alienation

Percentage within level of alienation		Level of alienation					Total
		Low	Below average	Average	Above average	High	
Most prevailing culture in the organization	Clan	24.7%	16.9%	9.8%	14.9%	2.8%	15.7%
	Adhocracy	10.6%	4.2%	13.1%	8.5%	11.1%	9.3%
	Market	20.0%	38.0%	16.4%	34.0%	5.6%	24.0%
	Hierarchy	44.7%	40.8%	60.7%	42.6%	80.6%	51.0%
Total		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 4. The percentage of most prevailing culture in the organization versus level of alienation

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings described have established that there is a strong inverse correlation between student alienation and organizational culture. Hence, it can be said that the culture of an educational institution will have a great influence on the experience and engagement of students. Therefore, in order to reduce alienation among the youth effective steps should be taken at the institutional level. This fact suggests that all educational institutions should conduct an assessment of their own cultures and make necessary changes for improving the overall experience of the students and to give the youth a sense of belonging, commitment and direction in their lives [32].

A moderate negative correlation is observed between student alienation and clan culture of the organization ($r=-0.448$). This indicates that students are less alienated if the institution has more of a clan culture in the campus life. Students are expecting educational institutes to function more as large family than corporate culture. It demands collaborative, commonality, and consensus features in the campus life [33].

The regression analysis indicates that 29.1% of the student alienation is explained by organization culture. Which is almost one third of it and certainly universities need to work towards having a better organizational culture which can reduced student alienation. Adjusted R square value indicates that adding more independent variables would explain 28.6% of student alienation. From the cross-tabulation analysis, it is clear that, student alienation increases if the organization has hierarchy culture. However, students seem to ignore the market culture shown by the organizations and did not feel much alienated. It could be due to the acceptance and helplessness upon prevailing dominant commodity perspectives of the newly founded universities [34].

Though the alienation level is average and not very high among students of selected University, it is necessary that the institution looks into this aspect [35]. The mean score suggests that the alienation level is average. However, when we look at the number of students falling in each category of alienation, it is observed that almost a total of 288 students belong to the average, above average, and high levels of alienation. This tells us that half the sample of students feels alienated to certain extent and are to be taken care. A deeper analysis in this aspect is certainly needed.

Similarly, the score for organizational culture as rated by students is average. Students have rated the culture here as one characterized by the philosophy of market culture and hierarchical culture. Majority of students feel that the university has a very hierarchical culture and approach to all the activities. The lowest rated culture was adhocracy which means that students do not feel free and independent. They might not be allowed to be creative and innovative and that the institution might not have been very open to change. This would imply that in this Institution there is more of impersonality and less of common values and familial bonding that can keep the members together. This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Anderson which says that bureaucratization and hierarchical factors in the climate of an institution can lead to higher level of alienation among students. This certainly points to the need and scope for improvement. It is highly advisable for all educational institutions to build up cultures that have aspects of clan and adhocracy [36]. This leads to growth and hence university has to work in this direction.

In the study, the market and hierarchy are the types of culture that have been marked as being more prevalent. If these aspects are continuously marked as being more prevalent, then it can have a simultaneous increase in the levels of alienation among the students as well. This is in consistent with the theoretical approaches provided by Mann [37]. One of the social perspectives says that alienation is due to the focus on educating oneself for utilitarianism, instrumentalism, performance and consumption. According to Mann, this is one of the factors that can lead to alienation. If market culture is rated high then this is certainly one of the

perspectives that will come up. Mann also puts forth that one of the factors also includes the power relationship between teaching and learning and the loss of ownership felt by the students. When students are positioned in a hierarchy based on the assessment and examinations that also becomes an important factor in giving rise to feelings of alienation. Hence, the institution should make ample amount of efforts to reduce the characteristics of market and hierarchy and have more features of clan and adhocracy while creating, establishing, and sustaining the culture.

It is an important growing institute in the present context and that periodic assessment of the culture and well-being of students will take the institution to greater heights. This idea is supported by the study conducted by Eze wherein he proposes that an educational institution can progress and reach newer heights if the positive culture of the college is retained [13].

4. CONCLUSION

An educational institution is not only responsible for the transmission of knowledge and providing degrees to its students. It has the major function of providing an atmosphere that enhances student well-being and assures that students have developed in a holistic manner. Hence every educational institution should shape and mould its culture in such a way that the students feel engaged and involved and not alienated. Students should get a sense of direction and meaning in lives when they come out of a higher education institution. This study presented that there is a high inverse correlation between student alienation and organizational culture in the university. It was also shown that hierarchy (clan) is the most prevalent culture in this educational institution. As it is a growing institution and such studies would certainly add to its growth. Hence, it is necessary that every educational institution takes up periodic assessment of its culture and well-being of students in order to identify the problems concerning alienation and improve the culture. This study has made an important contribution to the existing literature by emphasizing organizational culture in Universities in the Indian context and by opening a new discussion about the students' perception of the culture. The study is also of significant value as it deals with a very relevant issue of alienation among the youth and provides suggestions to develop cultures that are conducive for students' engagement.

Every study is bound to have certain limitations. One of the limitations of the study is that the participants selected from one institution only and hence it is challenging to generalize the results to other institutions. Cultures of several institutions can be studied in order to arrive at reliable arguments about the influence of organizational cultures on students' experiences and engagement. Another limitation of the study is that various demographic variables are not considered. For instance, students coming from the same city and those belonging to other parts of the country might gain completely different experiences on the campus and thus, the further research on this idea must integrate various demographic variables. The author calls for further research on understanding the impact of organizational culture on students' engagement and experiences and shaping the ideal culture accordingly.

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